

dish culture. It was also evident that elongation was greater at higher seeding depths in all the test genotypes. On the contrary, the length of the second leaf blade as measured in seedlings raised under normal pot culture showed a reverse trend, i.e., the length was less for deepwater rice genotypes than for nondeepwater types.

These two seedling characters were used as morphological markers to evaluate germplasm and segregating lines for tolerance for deepwater conditions in our subsequent experiments. ■

Tolerance for submergence in rainfed lowland rice under repetition of flooding

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In South and Southeast Asia, rainfed lowland rice is generally affected by submergence during flash floods when the plant remains completely under water. The frequency and duration of floods differ from place to place and year to year, causing different degrees of plant mortality. Information on tolerance for single submergence is available, but it is lacking on cultivar survival because of recycling of flooding. These experiments were conducted to identify rice cultivars that could withstand different cycles of flooding.

The experiments were carried out during the wet season with 242 cultivars of the Assam Rice Collection (ARC), which is considered to be a rich source of germplasm because of its high degree of phenotypic divergence. The genotypes were direct-seeded with a spacing of 20 × 10 cm. Two seedlings hill⁻¹ were maintained by thinning after 10 d of germination. Twenty-day-old seedlings were submerged for 12 d under 60 cm of water followed by normal conditions with 10 cm of water. After 10 d from the removal of water pressure, that is, 42 d after sowing, a severe submergence treatment was

given to the regenerated seedlings for another 10 d under 80 cm of water. A survival count was taken visually immediately after drainage of the water, and was confirmed after 15 d.

Dissolved oxygen concentration was measured using a submersible polarographic oxygen electrode (Syland Model 610, Heppenheim, Germany). Light transmission was measured using a quantum underwater light sensor (Licor, Model 185B).

To determine yield and yield-contributing characters, an experiment was conducted under rainfed lowland conditions where water depth varied between 0 and 50 cm.

Light penetration inside the floodwater was comparatively less in second submergence than in first submergence, which suggested that the floodwater was more turbid during second submergence. Oxygen concentration

measured around 12 noon was above the air saturation (>7.36 ppm) level (Table 1), but susceptible checks were ruined because of the severe pressure of submergence (Table 2).

After second submergence, a few genotypes survived. Survival percentage was maximum in Matia (87%), followed by FR13A (85%), CR380-10 (60%), and ARC18112 (56%) and 18101 (51%). Sabita, a submergence-tolerant cultivar, identified earlier on the basis of single-submergence treatment, showed only 35% survival. After first submergence, when water receded, the elongated top leaves descended to the ground and ultimately decayed. Therefore, plant height just before second submergence was less than the height just after the completion of first submergence.

Yield and yield-contributing characters showed great variation

Table 1. Floodwater characteristics at around 12 noon. Data given as mean +SE.

Water depth (cm)	Days after first submergence			Days after second submergence		
	2	5	9	2	5	5
<i>Light transmission (%)</i>						
5	72.6 ± 0.4	70.4 ± 0.3	73.3 ± 1.2	68.4 ± 0.3	67.1 ± 0.6	62.2 ± 0.3
30	62.2 ± 0.6	64.5 ± 0.9	62.3 ± 1.0	56.0 ± 0.7	53.6 ± 1.1	45.9 ± 0.4
60	53.7 ± 0.5	53.6 ± 0.4	53.5 ± 1.0	50.1 ± 0.4	42.2 ± 1.1	37.6 ± 0.4
Mean	62.8	62.8	63.0	58.2	54.3	48.6
<i>Oxygen concentration (ppm)</i>						
5	7.37 ± 0.02	7.92 ± 0.14	7.40 ± 0.07	7.65 ± 0.04	7.82 ± 0.03	7.95 ± 0.05
30	7.47 ± 0.06	7.75 ± 0.13	7.57 ± 0.02	7.57 ± 0.01	7.77 ± 0.04	7.90 ± 0.05
60	7.92 ± 0.02	7.50 ± 0.12	7.55 ± 0.04	7.95 ± 0.03	7.90 ± 0.02	7.72 ± 0.05
Mean	7.59	7.72	7.51	7.72	7.83	7.86

Table 2. Survival percentage and changes in plant height because of repetition of flooding.

Germplasm/ cultivar	Seedling height (cm)				Survival (%) after second submergence
	First submergence		Second submergence		
	Before	After	Before	After	
FR13A	23	76	48	72	85
Sabita	29	97	44	74	35
CR380-10	34	100	53	98	60
Matia	35	107	61	100	87
ARC18112	27	91	34	86	56
ARC18101	28	90	41	85	51
ARC18104	28	87	36	83	46
ARC18172	32	91	41	81	42
ARC18198	29	83	42	80	40
Tulasi	25	70	34	52	03
Mahsuri	23	76	35	63	02
Mean	26	88	43	79	46

Table 3. Grain yield and its contributing characters under waterlogged (0-50 cm depth) conditions.

Germplasm/ cultivar	Plant height (cm)	Days to 90% flowering	Single panicle weight (g)	PBT ^a (no. m ⁻²)	Harvest index (%)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)
FR13A	158	145	3.63	135	23.1	386
Sabita	184	141	4.46	95	31.0	421
CR380-10	169	149	4.20	138	33.5	472
Matia	178	149	2.58	110	21.6	215
ARC18112	154	98	2.59	118	24.9	260
ARC18101	158	121	3.03	100	31.2	261
ARC18104	152	131	3.75	104	29.4	347
ARC18172	185	110	2.50	109	27.9	212
ARC18198	122	92	2.34	133	38.4	267
Tulasi	145	141	4.23	153	29.4	516
Mean	160	128	3.33	119	29.0	336
CV	11.4	15.8	23.2	15.2	16.3	30.8

^aPBT = panicle-bearing tillers.

(Table 3). For the rainfed lowlands of eastern India, plants with different maturity periods are desirable for different locations. Therefore, plant breeders could employ the genotypes mentioned here. ■

Comments. If you have comments or suggestions about the IRRN, please write to the editor.

Yield potential

Physiological basis of heterosis in rice

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New plant types and hybrids are physiologically more efficient. They have a higher biomass than inbred varieties and a comparable harvest index. Increasing biomass yield and maintaining a high harvest index are the main breeding strategies for achieving another breakthrough in rice yield. Biomass is a complex trait governed by a number of morphophysiological components. We attempted to analyze the physiological components of biomass and to study the character association and path relationship among its components. A strategy to select parents for developing hybrids and pedigree breeding based on physiological efficiency are outlined.

The material for this study consisted of 15 F₁s and 6 parents from a 6 × 6 half diallel involving diverse parents for physiological efficiency. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Data were recorded on characters such as biological yield, grain yield, harvest index, days to 50% flowering, grain-filling duration, days to maturity, cumulative growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation

rate (NAR), leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area duration (LAD), and leaf area plant⁻¹ at different growth stages. Correlation, path effects, and heterosis were estimated.

Grain yield, CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area at seedling, tillering, flowering, and maturity showed a highly significant positive association with biological yield. The cross, Jaya / Swarnaprabha, which exhibited a high heterobeltiosis for biological yield (54.9%), also showed a significant positive heterosis for grain yield, harvest index, CGR, LAI, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Characters that showed a negative association with biological yield did not exhibit any positive heterosis. It is therefore evident that, to develop heterotic hybrids, we should identify parents with high physiological efficiency in terms of CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Because characters such as NAR, LAR, LAD, and leaf area showed a high positive direct path effect, direct selection for these traits should be effective.

With this understanding of the key physiological determinants of biological yield, the interrelationship among these components, and their direct and indirect effects on biological yield, we can make a better selection of parents. This approach should help develop superior hybrids and generate valuable breeding material for pedigree selection. ■

Physiological efficiency of rice hybrids

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Heterosis observed in hybrids is the result of various physiological processes that occur at different stages of plant growth. A precise knowledge of the factors that contribute to heterotic vigor would help to manipulate heterosis expression in hybrids. We made a study to assess the physiological efficiency of rice hybrids during the crop growth period and to analyze the factors that contribute to heterosis expression. Six promising experimental rice hybrids were evaluated along with the popular check varieties Samba Mahsuri and Chaitanya during the 1995 wet season. Crop growth rate (CGR), leaf area index (LAI), and biomass production (BMP) were estimated at 15-d intervals from 15 to 60 d after planting (DAP). Harvest index (HI) and grain yield were recorded at harvest.

CGR increased up to 45 DAP and decreased later in all hybrids and checks. LAI, however, consistently increased from 15 to 60 DAP and hybrids recorded a higher LAI from 30 DAP onward compared with the checks. The high initial CGR was not maintained to the later growth stages